

The Consequence of Material Inhomogeneity on the Strain Response of Automated Tow Placed Structures With Stress Concentrations

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Abstract

The influence of inhomogeneous microstructure on the fracture properties are presented in this study. Previous tests have shown an improvement in the notched tensile strength of laminates manufactured with fiber placement versus hand layup for the same materials and laminate configuration. Fiber placement results in structures with a more inhomogeneous microstructure than in conventional hand layup manufacturing. Equivalent continuum modeling was employed to study this phenomenon. A specialty, couple stress (Cosserat Theory) finite element was developed to explore the influence of inhomogeneities in regions of high stress gradients such as notches. The results indicate that the addition of the couple stresses mitigates singularities at notch tips. A two-parameter failure criterion, based on critical strain energy release rates and an inhomogeneity parameter, is proposed. Good correlations were found between predictions and experimental results.

Impetus

As advanced composites continue to be utilized in large, primary structure, a need exists to develop an understanding of the influence of processing and manufacturing on fracture performance. Structures are typically manufactured from thin, (0.127 mm) macroscopically-homogeneous prepreg tape (305 mm wide), laminated and cured in an autoclave. Obviously, manufacturing large structures with even moderate volume production schedules will require alternative processing and material forms. One such alternative is Fiber Placement (FP) (also known as Automated Tow Placement, ATP). This manufacturing technique has the advantage that fabrication production rates may be increased and the production may be automated. This fabrication method, as developed by Hercules, is shown in Figure 1.

In Figure 1, individual tows are placed on a creel and passed through a robotic head. A rotational axis, along with manipulation of the robotic head, allows placement of these individual tows. Unlike conventional filament winding, where compaction is provided via tensioning of the tows, fiber placement provides compaction via roller pressure. This versatility allows for manufacturing structures which are not axisymmetric and may even contain concave surfaces. Consequently, the designer is not constrained to near geodesic paths. In addition, individual tow cut and add allows for in-situ thickness control. These individual tows allow for intra-ply hybridization as well.

This manufacturing process results in a tow to tow architecture which is different from standard prepreg tape laminated structures. Small gaps and laps can form between the tows (bundles of fibers), which are approximately 2.54 mm wide and between bands (arrays of tows), which are 30 mm or greater. This can result in localized inhomogeneities in a repeatable pattern. This is illustrated in Figure 2 for a $[-45/+45/90/+30/-30/0]_s$ laminate configuration. Figure 2 is a Computer Aided Design (CAD) generated model of the ply by ply and tow by tow buildup in a localized region of a structure. Each line represents the a characteristic of the laminate microstructure created during fiber placement. Regions where lines cross indicate a coupling of the microstructural characteristics between plies of differing orientations. The regions where lines cross represent potential lap/gap sites. The minimum spacing between this crossing is approximately 1.5 tow widths or 3.8 mm. As a result, this manufacturing process introduces another level of inhomogeneity which is greater than the fiber/matrix level of inhomogeneity or thickness of individual plies. As with other alternative forms such as woven materials, it is improper to view fiber placement as a material form, especially with respect to fracture. It represents an independent substructure. Therefore, a need exists to understand the influence of this inhomogeneity on performance.

As an example of applications, the fiber placement architecture can result in improved fracture properties under tensile loading as shown in Figure 3 [1]. This improvement has the largest influence on decreasing weight with improved costs for Boeing's advanced fuselage designs compared to conventional prepreg tape laminates. These comparisons were made from the same materials, the only difference being in the manufacturing process. The motivation behind this study is to explore equivalent continuum modeling of inhomogeneities to predict the tensile fracture performance of fiber placed (or other inhomogeneous) structures.

Background

Recent work in utilizing theory of elasticity with couple stresses for modeling materials with inhomogeneous microstructures has shown promise for developing equivalent continuum mechanics approaches in lieu of modeling each individual phase. In particular, Toupin challenges the basic concepts and principles of the mechanics of continuous media [2]. Nakamura and Lakes have shown the utility of this approach for constitutive modeling, while Wang and Chen have utilized micropolar theory as an additional parameter in fracture on the basis of empirical studies [3-6]. Consequently, proper treatment of these couplings may be necessary for accurate stress and strain descriptions.

Theory of Elasticity, including couple stresses, is not a new idea. Cosserat and Cosserat developed equations for this phenomenon in 1909 [7]. The addition of couple stresses has been rekindled from time to time, and is sometimes denoted as micropolar theory. However, there has been little impetus to develop the theory since the level of inhomogeneity of typical structural materials is very small. The low level of inhomogeneity for most engineering materials has made material property measurements difficult and has resulted in this approach being of only academic interest.

Below is reiterated the two dimensional theory (in the absence of body forces) as developed by Eringen [8]. Consider an element with the loadings as shown in Figure 4. In this figure, the normal tractions are present with the addition of moments m_{xz} and m_{yz} on a local basis. These are simply additional stress terms and obey all of the laws for regular stress tensors. The equilibrium equations (neglecting higher order terms) are as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}\Sigma F_x = 0: \quad & \frac{\partial \sigma_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yx}}{\partial y} = 0 \\ \Sigma F_y = 0: \quad & \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_y}{\partial y} = 0\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

$$\Sigma M_0 = 0: \quad \frac{\partial m_{xz}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial m_{yz}}{\partial y} + \tau_{xy} - \tau_{yx} = 0$$

The last equation is a consequence of the local moments. Note that local gradients in couple stresses yield an additional equilibrium equation where τ_{xy} is not equal to τ_{yx} as in normal planar equilibrium.

During deformation, the gradients in displacements may be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}u_{rj} &= \frac{1}{2}(u_{rj} + u_{jr}) + \frac{1}{2}(u_{rj} - u_{jr}) \\ &\quad \text{or} \\ u_{rj} &= \epsilon_{ij} + \omega_{ij}\end{aligned}\tag{2}$$

In small displacement, small strain elasticity, the first term represents the strain tensor. In words, this is the displacement gradient tensor minus the antisymmetric, rotational tensor.

Eringen introduced an additional, independent rotation vector ϕ to define the following strain-displacement relationship.

$$\epsilon_{ij} = u_{rj} - \epsilon_{ijk}\phi_k\tag{3}$$

where ϵ_{ijk} is the permutation tensor.

Analogous to the above, this is the gradient in displacement tensor minus an independent, in-plane rotation. This definition of kinematics was utilized for this study. The microcurvatures are gradients of the rotations. Equation 3 represents the general, three-dimensional strain tensor. However, for the remainder of this paper and for examples, the treatment will be two-dimensional.

In composites, strong elastic couplings may make the constitutive relationships more complicated. In the most general two-dimensional form, the constitutive properties can be represented as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \\ \tau_{yx} \\ m_x \\ m_y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & C_{14} & CB_{15} & CB_{16} \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{23} & C_{24} & CB_{25} & CB_{26} \\ C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} & C_{34} & CB_{35} & CB_{36} \\ C_{41} & C_{42} & C_{43} & C_{44} & CB_{45} & CB_{46} \\ CB_{51} & CB_{52} & CB_{53} & CB_{54} & B_{55} & CB_{56} \\ CB_{61} & CB_{62} & CB_{63} & CB_{64} & CB_{65} & B_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \epsilon_{xy} \\ \epsilon_{yx} \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \end{pmatrix}\tag{4}$$

where the C_{ij} matrix is from normal lamination theory the B_{ij} terms are the micro bending stiffness terms, and the CB_{ij} are couple stiffness terms. Notice in Equation 4 that the units on normal membrane stiffnesses are F/L^2 . The consistent units on micro-moments are FL/L^2 . This means that the consistent stiffness has units FL/L or simply F . Consequently, these terms follow a different scaling parameter than normal membrane stiffnesses by a factor of L^2 . As inhomogeneities become small (i.e. grain sizes in metals), the influence of the coupling is negligible [9]. However, as inhomogeneities increase, the bending terms have greater significance. This will be illustrated below via examples.

Some additional thought must be given to the physical significance and development of the coupling terms. Equation 4 is a 6x6 matrix (21 independent stiffness terms from reciprocity), and is as complicated as a fully three-dimensional constitutive property matrix in normal elasticity. Clearly, one could expend considerable efforts to characterize these constitutive terms. However, for this study, only the B_{55} and B_{66} terms were utilized, with all other CB_{ij} equal to zero.

Finite Element Implementation

With equilibrium, kinematics, and constitutive properties defined, it is a simple matter to formulate finite elements based on couple stress theory. For displacement based finite elements, standard interpolating polynomials (shape functions) were utilized and implemented via successive multiplications of the discretized strain-displacement and constitutive matrices [10]. In this manner, a two-dimensional, general Cosserat element was developed for this study.

To illustrate the influence of the moment terms, consider an isotropic plate under plane stress conditions with an open hole. Two different hole sizes ($r=3.18\text{mm}$, $r=6.35\text{mm}$) were studied with a constant width to diameter (W/D) ratio of 4.0. The plate was assumed to be made of aluminum with an elastic modulus of 67 GPa and a poisson's ratio of 0.3.

A Cosserat length was utilized to describe the inhomogeneity. These lengths, defined here as λ , were 0.0mm (homogeneous case), 2.54mm and 8.38mm. Using the L^2 scaling rule discussed above, these lengths resulted in bending stiffness terms (B_{55} and B_{66} in Equation 1) equal to 0.01 and 0.1 times the elastic modulus. All other CB_{ij} couplings (off-diagonal CB_{ij} terms in Equation 4) were assumed to be 0.0. Of some interest, the C_{33} and C_{44} for an isotropic material are equal to 2G to maintain equivalent strain energies to isotropic materials under pure shear with no Cosserat behavior.

The ratios of near field to far field σ_y at y equal to 0.0 (i.e., the open hole stress concentration factor K_T) are shown in Figure 5. Notice that the baseline, homogeneous case yields a K_T of 3.0. If these results were plotted with normal isotropic equations, with no Cosserat parameters, they would collapse onto a single line. However, as the level of inhomogeneity and absolute hole size is changed, the K_T is decreased. While results such as these are not new, they illustrate the effect of the couple stress terms on stress at a hole.

Notice also that not only are stress concentrations affected, but that the gradients (rate of decrease in stress concentration) are affected as well. This effect of the addition of couple stresses on gradients has also been noted by Sternberg [11]. The baseline case drops below the case for the lowest K_T along the net ligament. This is somewhat intuitive, since both cases have the same equilibrium conditions where the integral of σ_y along the length is equivalent in all cases.

Discussion on Applications to Fracture of Composites

As was stated in the Impetus section, an improvement in notched tensile fracture was found between the fiber-placed and conventional, hand layup panels which were manufactured from the same materials. The Cosserat element described above was utilized to model the influence of inhomogeneity on fracture.

Tensile coupons with a central notch were analyzed and tested. This coupon is a half symmetry model, in lieu of a quarter symmetry model, to allow for the potential of membrane and membrane-curvature couplings (which were not studied here). The layup was [+45/-45/0/90/+30/-30/0], AS4/3501-6 [12]. Classical lamination theory was used for the membrane stiffnesses, while only diagonal bending terms were introduced as above. These were introduced by the Cosserat length scaling parameter λ^2 , as above. No coupling between the membrane terms and the bending terms were used. Various notch sizes and Cosserat lengths were examined.

Strain Energy Release Rate - Basis for Comparisons

As was illustrated above in the example problem for the hole above, Cosserat theory affects stresses and stress gradients. Consequently, the strain energy release rate for crack propagation is expected to be affected as well. The strain energy release rate can be considered as the driving force for crack extension and was used as the basis for comparison of the results. From Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM), failure is assumed to occur when the critical strain energy release rate (a material parameter) is exceeded.

The crack tip closure method was employed to calculate strain energy release rates [13]. This method is illustrated for Mode I in Figure 6. The Mode I strain energy release rate is simply the work required for closure divided by the area created during propagation. The Cosserat theory introduces an additional moment term required to ensure that rotations are zero. Hence, the Mode I strain energy release rate (G_I) is:

$$G_I = \frac{F\Delta y + M\Delta\theta}{2b\Delta a} \quad (5)$$

where F is the force required to close the crack

Δy is the crack opening displacement

M is the moment required for zero rotation at the crack tip

$\Delta\theta$ is the total independent rotation

b is the width

and Δa is the crack extension.

Additional terms for the work required to close the crack are necessary if additional couplings exist. However, it was noted that the contribution from moments (the second term in G_I in Equation 5) was negligible (two orders of magnitude less) than the work required to close the crack, even for large Cosserat parameters.

The influence of the Cosserat theory on total strain energy release rate (normalized to width and the square of stress) for various crack sizes and Cosserat parameters is shown in Figure 7. The baseline, homogeneous case has a steeper slope with increasing crack length and is higher for all crack sizes. This indicates greater notch sensitivity.

Applications to Failure

Predictions were made for hand layup and fiber-placed laminates with notches. A constant value for critical strain energy release rate, G_{CH} of 225.1 MJ/m², was used for both the hand layup and tow-placed laminates, and is postulated to be a material constant for these AS4/3501-6 laminates. An inhomogeneity parameter λ^2 of 0.32cm² was used for the hand layup results (low inhomogeneity) and an inhomogeneity parameter λ^2 of 6.4 cm² (high inhomogeneity) was used for the fiber-placed laminates. The comparisons between experimental results and predictions are illustrated in Figure 8. In Figure 8, the data points are the mean with a given crack size with the range in data indicated with the error bars. The 0.32 cm² is an empirical factor to match the experimental data. From previous work on measurements of stiffness, the Cosserat length does not necessarily have to correspond to the physical size of the inhomogeneity and therefore, can be considered as an independent parameter [5,6].

The above model is a two parameter model, with the empirically determined values of critical strain energy release rate G_{CH} and inhomogeneity parameter λ^2 . Loads are introduced at the structural level, but fracture always occurs at the local level. As a result, the approach presented above offers the potential of providing additional scaling information for materials with inhomogeneous microstructure. That is, the inhomogeneity parameter may be a material constant based on the manufacturing technique. This warrants further investigation.

Conclusions and Future Work

The influence of manufacturing has a significant effect on fracture strength in composite structures. A general, two-dimensional finite element with couple stresses has been developed to study the effects of material inhomogeneity on stresses and regions of stress gradients. The results indicate that geometry alone is not sufficient for providing information with respect to scaling. This result has implications for scaling data from the coupon level to the subcomponent level to full-scale structures. Empirically-determined critical strain energy release rates, combined with an experimentally-determined inhomogeneity parameter λ^2 yields good experimental/analytical correlations and provides a basis for comparing the damage tolerance of laminates from different manufacturing techniques.

Clearly, these results are preliminary, and the practicality of this equivalent continuum modeling of inhomogeneous microstructure will require more studies and correlations with experimental data. Specifically, independent measurements of the Cosserat terms are required. Since the Cosserat parameter has a profound influence on the gradient at the crack tip, measurements of strain decay may provide empirical measurements for λ^2 . Also, additional independent material property measurements such as wave dispersion and independent microrotations may provide independent measurements of the λ^2 as well [14].

References

1. Cairns, D.S., Walker, T., Ilcewicz, L.B., "Response of Automated Tow Placement Laminates to Stress Concentrations," proceedings of the **Third Advanced Composites Technology Conference**, June, 1992.
2. Toupin, R.A., "Theories of Elasticity with Couple-Stress," **Arch. Rational Mech. Anal.**, Vol. 17, no. 2, 1964, pp. 85-112.

3. Nakamura, S. and Lakes, R.S., "Finite Element Analysis of Stress Concentration Around a Blunt Crack in a Cosserat Elastic Solid," **Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering**, Vol. 66, 1988, pp. 257-266.
4. Nakamura, S., Benedict, R., and Lakes, R., "Finite Element Method for Orthotropic Micropolar Elasticity," **Int. J. Engng. Sci.**, Vol 22, No. 3, 1984, pp. 319-330.
5. Lakes, R.S., "Experimental microelasticity for two porous solids," **International Journal of Solids and Structures**, 22, 1986, pp. 55-63.
6. Wang, C. and Chen, Z.D., "Microrotation analysis applied to material cracking and toughness," **International Journal of Fracture**, Vol. 54, 1992, pp. 359-369.
7. Cosserat, E. and Cosserat, F., **Théorie des corps déformables**, Hermann and Cie, Paris, 1909, p. 137.
8. Eringen, A.C., "Linear theory of micropolar elasticity," **J. Math. Mech.**, **54**, 1966, pp. 909-923.
9. Ellis, R.W. and Smith, C.W., "A Thin-Plate Analysis and Experimental Evaluation of Couple-Stress Effects," **Exptl. Mech.**, Sept. 1967, pp. 372-380.
10. Cook, R.D., **Concepts and Applications of Finite Element Analysis**, John Wiley and Sons, New York, New York, 1981.
11. Sternberg, E., "Couple-Stresses and Singular Stress Concentrations in Elastic Solids," **Mechanics of Generalized Continua**, ed. by Kroner, Springer-Verlag, New York, Inc., New York, 1968, pp. 95-108.
12. **Hercules Prepreg Tape Materials Characterization Data Package**, Fibers: AS4, IM6, IM7 & IM8, Resins: 8551-7, 8551-7A, 8552, 3501-6, Hercules Composite Products Group, Magna, Utah, November, 1988.
13. Rybicki, E.F., and Kanninen, M.F., "A Finite Element Calculation of Stress Intensity Factors by a Modified Crack Closure Integral," **Engineering Fracture Mechanics**, Vol. 9, 1977.
14. Lakes, R.S., Personal Correspondence, September, 1992.

Figure 1. Fiber Placement (Automated Tow Placement) Process

CAD-generated local region

25.4 mm X 25.4 mm Region, 2.54 mm low width
[-45/+45/90/+30/-30/0]s AS4/3501-6

Cross-over points represent potential lap (overlap) or gap (space) regions

Figure 2. Resulting Fiber Placement Architecture

Tension Residual Strength Curves Normalized By Material Density

Figure 3. Improvement in Performance for Automated Tow Placement vs. Tape

Figure 4. Couple Stresses on a Differential Element

Figure 5. Stress Concentrations of Open Holes (with and without Cosserat Theory)

Figure 6. Crack Closure Method for Cosserat Element

Figure 7. Strain Energy Release Rate as a Function of Crack Size (with and without Cosserat Theory)

Figure 8. Effect of Cosserat Parameter (λ^2) on Strain Energy Release Rate